

Simultaneously refined i_d and $E_{1/2}$ Values for determining Stability Constants by Indirect Technique

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The stability constants of $Zn^{2+}-Na_2S_2O_3$ system determined by indirect ion technique were $\beta_1 = 20$, $\beta_2 = 220$ and $\beta_3 = 340$ and β_4 resulted in a negative value. Cd^{2+} was selected as indicator ion. The simultaneous refinement of $E_{1/2}$ and i_d by computation evaluation were used in calculating β values. The polarographic procedure was modified to include more accuracy and sensitivity compared to the conventional technique.

THE computer programming^{1,2} has long been recognised for treating the polarographic data for complex formation between metal ion and ligand, revealing improvement over the careful graphical analysis. Piljac *et al.*³ experienced that a system can be considered physically meaningful if the values of stability constants are positive and standard error of any constant should invariably be less than the constant itself.

In order to evaluate stability constants polarographically, it is important to note that simultaneous refinement in i_d and $E_{1/2}$, based on least-squares principle would meet all the requisites of accuracy and sensitivity, provided the experimental $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values are obtained with precision. Kivalo and Luoto⁴ and later Crow and Westwood⁵ employed indirect ion technique to evaluate the stability constants of irreversibly reduced labile complex systems. The technique was primarily developed by Schwarzenbach⁶ for non-labile and by Ringbom and Eriksson⁷ for labile complex systems. The applications of this process have not been explored fully. Therefore, a study of Zn^{2+} -thiosulphate system employing Cd^{2+} as indicator ion was undertaken.

The fundamental equation,

$$E_{d \text{ e}} = E_{1/2} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln (i (i_d - i)^{-1}) \quad (1)$$

can be rewritten as

$$E_d = A - C \ln (I_d (B - I_d)^{-1}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or, } I_d \exp(E_d/C) = B \exp(A/C) - I_d \exp(A/C) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{This is of the form, } Z_d = \beta - I_d \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } \beta = B \exp(A/C) \text{ and } \alpha = \exp(A/C) \quad (5)$$

and Z_d , I_d experimentally known and fitting N pairs of Z_d and I_d , a least-squares analysis may be made; β and α identified as

$$\beta/\alpha = B = i_d; C \ln \alpha = A = E_{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where, A and B are constants, their approximate

values A_0 and B_0 known experimentally. In order to satisfy equation (4) for N pair of values (Z_d, I_d) it would be necessary to utilise all the data to find the best estimate of α and β such as $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ which minimises S , the sum of squares of the deviations of observed Z_d from calculated, $Z_d = \beta - I_d \bar{\alpha}$. To determine these values, S (Ref. 8), is differentiated with respect to α and β , and the resulting equations are solved for $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\beta}$. Having determined standard errors and then using equations (6), the refined values of $E_{1/2}$ and i_d are obtained.

Experimental

An automatic pen recording polarograph (OH-105 Radelkis, Hungary) with a three-electrode circuitry, connected in series with a potentiometer (OSAW, India) and a conductivity bridge (Philips, India) to serve as indicator for detecting substantial changes in ionic strength, was employed to record polarograms. The DME had the capillary characteristics $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.09 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ in 0.1 M KCl when short-circuited. SCE was used as the reference electrode. The salt solutions were prepared in distilled water and standardised by chemical methods.

Polarographic procedure: A three-electrode polarographic cell was used for the experimental purpose. Accurately measured 10.0 cm^3 of solution P_1 (composition indicated in Table 1) was placed in the cell and P_2 was introduced in P_1 from the microburette. The solutions to be polarographed were deoxygenated by bubbling purified nitrogen for 5 min. The first polarogram (with P_1) was taken and a series of polarograms recorded after adding P_2 in small aliquots. The process was then reversed. $\mu = 5$ was maintained by adding requisite amounts of NaClO_4 . Similarly, 10.0 cm^3 of solution P_3 was placed in the cell and P_4 was run from the microburette into P_3 . The current-voltage curves were recorded in duplicate.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF SOLUTION

Solution	Composition 0.1 M KCl and 0.002% Triton X-100 kept constant in all solutions		
	Cd ^{II} M	Zn ^{II} M	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ M
P ₁	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	—	—
P ₂	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	—	1.5
P ₃	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	5 × 10 ⁻³	—
P ₄	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	5 × 10 ⁻³	1.5

Results and Discussion

The diffusion-controlled reduction behaviour was established from (i) $i_d \propto c$ (ii) $i_d \propto h^{1/2}$ and (iii) low temperature coefficient (1.56 % deg⁻¹).

The plot of $\log (i(i_d - i)^{-1})$ vs $E_{d,s}$ for Zn^{II} in KCl and Na₂S₂O₃ resulted in the curvatures, revealing thereby irreversible nature of the reduction process. Randles *et al.*⁹ approved similar reduction behaviour of Zn^{II} in this medium. Cd^{II} undergoes reversible reduction in the presence of Na₂S₂O₃ and $E_{1/2}$ shifts toward more negative potentials with increasing ligand concentration, consequently Cd^{II} was selected as the indicator ion for the study of Zn^{II}-Na₂S₂O₃ complexes.

The simultaneous determination of the refined $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values have been carried out with Hi-basic digital computer Spectrum-7/DCM (India) that provided 36-k byte words of auxiliary memory. The data evaluated by numerical treatment and graphically obtained are shown in Table 2. The

TABLE 2— $E_{1/2}$, i_d AND $2.303 RT/nF$ VALUES OF Cd-Na₂S₂O₃ SYSTEM*

(L)/M	$E_{1/2}$, i_d		$E_{1/2}$, i_d		$-2.303 RT/nF$ mV
	mV	μA	mV	μA	
	Graphically		Numerically		
0.068 1	610	3.50	612 ± 0.5	3.41 ± 0.05	29.6 ± 0.6
	608**	3.49	611 ± 0.5	3.34 ± 0.07	29.5 ± 0.2
0.10	615	3.37	620 ± 0.3	3.39 ± 0.05	29.8 ± 0.5
	614**	3.34	620 ± 0.7	3.40 ± 0.06	30.0 ± 0.5
0.173	622	3.36	630 ± 0.6	3.38 ± 0.04	29.5 ± 0.5
	625**	3.39	629 ± 0.2	3.38 ± 0.03	29.6 ± 0.1
0.240	638	3.36	642 ± 0.2	3.37 ± 0.02	29.25 ± 0.3
	642**	3.37	642 ± 0.4	3.38 ± 0.02	29.25 ± 0.4
0.315	650	3.34	660 ± 0.3	3.36 ± 0.02	29.1 ± 0.4
	655**	3.33	661 ± 0.5	3.37 ± 0.02	29.0 ± 0.5

* A part of the system.

** By repeating the same experiment.

value of C (equation 2) coincides with the theoretical value of 29.5 mV, predicting polarographic reversibility of the electrode process. The standard errors are small, showing the correctness of the measurement and accurate treatment. The duplicate measurements are in good accord to conclude that the solution preparation within the cell is 'superior' to that of the conventional method. There was rather no instant of eventuality of

drawing heavy currents throughout in this system, affecting pH and conductivity.

Simultaneous refinement in the experimental $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values over the purely graphical evaluation is substantially different and evidently minimises the error propagation in the calculation pattern of β values (Table 2). Fig. 1 depicts that

Fig. 1. Plots of $E_{1/2}$ for the Cd^{II}-Na₂S₂O₃ system in presence and absence of Zn^{II}.

$E_{1/2}$ shift of the indicator ion was smaller in the presence of Zn^{II} compared with its absence and this difference served as the basis for determining free ligand concentration. Thus Bjerrum function \bar{n} was calculated from the equation

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(\text{Total ligand concentration}) - (\text{Free ligand concentration})}{(\text{Concentration of metal ion})}$$

Concentrations of the free ligand and metal ions (indicator and competitive) as well as the calculated values of \bar{n} are listed in Table 3. The log plots of the free ligand concentration against \bar{n} resulted in maximum coordination number 4 (Fig. 2, Table 3) at higher ligand concentrations. The \bar{n} function

TABLE 3—FREE Na₂S₂O₃ AND \bar{n} VALUES FOR Zn-Na₂S₂O₃ SYSTEM (Cd^{II} 5 × 10⁻⁴ M, Zn^{II} 5 × 10⁻³ M)

(Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃) Total C _L M	(Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃) Free (L) M	log L	\bar{n}
0.025	0.012 5	-1.903 1	0.25
0.05	0.025	-1.602 1	0.50
0.075	0.040	-1.397	0.70
0.10	0.060	-1.221 8	0.80
0.2	0.15	-0.823 9	1.0
0.3	0.22	-0.657 6	1.6
0.4	0.28	-0.552 8	2.4
0.5	0.34	-0.468 5	3.2
0.8	0.60	-0.221 8	4.0
1.0	0.80	-0.096	4.0
1.2	1.00	0.00	4.0

Fig. 2. Formation curve of $Zn^{2+}-Na_2S_2O_3$ system showing $j=4$.

is related to the stability constants by the equation¹⁰,

$$\bar{n} = (1-\bar{n})(A)\beta_1 + (2-\bar{n})(A)^2\beta_2 + (3-\bar{n})(A)^3\beta_3$$

The following Rossotti plots result in

$$\beta_1 : (\bar{n})/(1-\bar{n})(A) \text{ vs } (2-\bar{n})(A)/(1-\bar{n})$$

$$\beta_2 : (\bar{n} + (\bar{n}-1)(A)\beta_1)/(2-\bar{n})(A)^2 \text{ vs } (3-\bar{n})(A)/(2-\bar{n})$$

$$\beta_3 : (\bar{n} + \dots + (\bar{n}-2)(A)^2\beta_2)/(3-\bar{n})(A)^3 \text{ vs } (4-\bar{n})(A)/(3-\bar{n})$$

$$\beta_4 : (\bar{n} + \dots + (\bar{n}-3)(A)^3\beta_3)/(4-\bar{n})(A)^4 \text{ vs } (5-\bar{n})(A)/(4-\bar{n})$$

β_1, β_2 and β_3 for $Zn^{2+}-Na_2S_2O_3$ as 20, 220 and 340, respectively. Gupta *et al.*¹¹ and Andreoli *et al.*¹² reported three values of β for Zn^{2+} with different ligands, which support this investigation. The failure of ascertaining the β_4 resulted from the Rossotti function diverged to negative value which has no physical significance³. The β values determined potentiometrically¹³, calorimetrically¹⁴, spectrophotometrically¹⁵ and conductometrically¹⁶ at various ionic strengths render difficulties to incorporate direct comparison. However, the order of values is within limits and do not differ substantially with the reported data, *e.g.* Aruga¹⁴ reported $\beta_1=13.2$ at $\mu=0.5$, whereas β_1 is 20.0 ($\mu=5.0$) in the present study.

Although Zn^{2+} has weak polarisation component, yet it possesses electrostatic active cation site which is likely to interact¹⁷ with thiosulphate anion to result in low β_1 . The second S atom in thiosulphate anion being attached loosely, enhances the covalent contribution in complexation to result in high β_2 compared to β_1 . The high $+\Delta H^\circ$ of the reaction¹⁴ due to cleavage of strong bond between cation and water of hydration with simultaneous inclusion of electronegative moiety could result in 3rd successive coordination complex. Since further nucleophilic substitution is least possible due to repulsive reactivity characteristics, it is difficult to compute β_4 .

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References

1. D. L. MCMASTER and W. B. SCHAAP, *Proc. Indiana Acad. Sci.*, 1958, 67, 111, 117.
2. L. MEITES, *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 733.
3. I. PILJAC, B. GRABARIC and I. FILIPOVIC, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1973, 42, 433.
4. P. KIVALO and R. LUOTO, *Suomen Kemistilehti, B*, 1957, 30, 163.
5. D. R. CROW and J. V. WESTWOOD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 179.
6. G. SCHWARZENBACH and H. ACKERMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 35, 485.
7. A. RINGBOM and L. ERIKSSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1953, 7, 1105.
8. V. B. VOUK, P. K. KARMALKAR and O. A. WEBER, *Arh. Kem.*, 1955, 27, 9.
9. J. E. B. RANGLES and W. K. SOMERTON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 48, 937.
10. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 1166.
11. O. D. GUPTA, K. D. GUPTA, S. C. BHAGEL and J. N. GAUR, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1978, 27, 265.
12. R. ANDREOLI, G. BATTISTUZZI GAVIOLI, L. BENEDETTI, G. GRANDI, G. MARCOTRIGIANO, L. MENABUB and G. C. PELLACANI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 46, 215.
13. H. PERSSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1970, 24, 3739.
14. R. ARUGA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 3779.
15. F. G. R. GIMBLETT and C. B. MONK, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 51, 793.
16. T. O. DENNEY and C. B. MONK, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 992.
17. H. WEINSTEIN, S. TOPIOL and R. OSMAN, *Jerusalem Symp. Quantum Chem. Biochem.*, 1981, 14, 383.